

Curriculum Vitae for Jacob Rosenberg.

Publikationer - artikler

Videnskabelige publikationer, disputats.

"Late postoperative hypoxaemia - mechanisms and clinical implications". Københavns Universitet. Lægeforeningens Forlag, København: 1994.

Artikler publiceret i videnskabelige tidsskrifter med peer review.

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- 13b. Rosenberg J, Ullstad T, Larsen PN, Moesgaard F, Kehlet H. Continuous assessment of oxygen saturation and subcutaneous oxygen tension following abdominal surgery - correction. *Eur J Surg* 1991; 157: 301.
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